

कृति रक्षा

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A STEP TOWARDS THE RECONSTRUCTION OF THE TEXT OF THE NĀṬYAŚĀSTRA OF BHARATA

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The *Nāṭyaśāstra* attributed to *Bharata* not only deals with stagecraft, but it has an extensive scope of other various related areas of science like that of music, classical Indian dance, and poetics as well. It also covers stage design, makeup, and virtually every other aspect of stagecraft. It is very important to the history of Indian classical music and dramaturgy because it is the only text which gives such convoluted details about the music both vocal and instrumental, as well as almost all the aspects of stage craft, i.e. beginning from the architecture of the play house to the staging of a play. Thus, an argument can be made that the *Natya Shastra* is the foundation of the performing art in India.

Although my study will centre around the Study on the major variants of the text of the *Nāṭyaśāstra*, still I think it to be pertinent to peep in to the significant editions & recensions of *Nāṭyaśāstra*.

1. Hall in his edition of *Dasarūpaka* published chapters XVIII-XX of *Nāṭyaśāstra* based on a single manuscript as appendices to it in *Bibliothica Indica* Series, Calcutta, 1865.¹
2. P. Regnaud, a French scholar published parts of Chapters XV-XVII of *Nāṭyaśāstra*, dealing with prosody, based on a different manuscript in the *Annels De Musee Guimet* in 1884 followed by publication of Chapters VI & VII
3. J. Grosset a pupil of P. Regnaud published chapter XVIII of *Nāṭyaśāstra* on music, having title as “*contribution l’e’tude de la Musique Hindoo*” in 1888 followed by Chapters I – XIV in 1898.
4. Pandit Shivadatta and Kashinath Pandurang Parav on the base of two other manuscripts published 37 chapters of *Nāṭyaśāstra* under *Kāvyamālā* edition in 1894.³
5. M. Ramakrishna Kavi published the *Nāṭyaśāstra* (37 Chapters) with *abhinavabhāratī* on the base of 40 manuscripts in *Gaekward Oriental series* in 1926, a second edition of which was brought out by K.S.Ramaswami Sastri in 1956.⁴
6. Pandit Batukanath Sharma and Pandit Baladeva Upadhyaya published a complete edition with 36 chapters based on two different manuscripts of *Nāṭyaśāstra* in the *Kāśī Sanskrit series* mostly quoted as *Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series* in 1929.
7. Prof. Kamalesh Datta Tripathy and his team are now working with another recent edition of *Nāṭyaśāstra* with 35 chapters based on *Newari* scripts collected from

Nāṭyaśāstra same year.²

1 P.V.Kane, *History of Sanskrit Poetics*, Motilal Banarasi Dass, Delhi, India, Reprint of the fourth edition, 1987. page-11.
2 Ibid. and Prof. Puspendra Kumar, introduction page – XIX, *Nāṭyaśāstra* translated in to English by M.M.Ghosh, New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, India, 2006.
3 P.V.Kane, *History of Sanskrit Poetics*, Motilal Banarasi Dass, Delhi, India, Reprint of the fourth edition, 1987. page-10.
4 Ibid. Page – 11.

Nepal, claiming to be the earliest manuscripts so far collected.

But the text of *Nāṭyaśāstra* is not yet substantiated as what should be the primary one. The editions of the same do not agree with a common and a uniform text. In India the very famous *Kāvyamālā* edition contains 37 chapters, where as another counterpart of the same, i.e. *Chowkhamba* edition contains 36. Abhinavagupta mentions in his commentary *Abhinavabhāraṭī*, that the text of *Nāṭyaśāstra* contains 36 chapters and six thousand (6,000) shlokas composed in *anuṣṭub* metre. As *Abhinavagupta* mentions in his second introductory verse of *Abhinavabhāraṭī* षट्त्रिंशत्कं भरतसूत्रमिदं विवृण्वन्वन्दे शिवं श्रुतितदर्थविवेकिधाम॥⁵ and also in the commentary to 6th verse of Chapter one as: मध्येऽत्र षट्त्रिंशदध्याख्या वयं तु ब्रूमः- नात्र क्रमः कश्चित्। अपि तु यथावसरं महावाक्यात्मना षट्साहस्रीरूपेण प्रधानतया प्रश्नपञ्चकनिरूपणपरेण शास्त्रेण तत्त्वं निर्णीयते।⁶

Ramakrishna Kavi prepares his text of *Nāṭyaśāstra* on the base of 40 manuscripts collected from different parts of India, in his preface to his edition of *Nāṭyaśāstra* divides all those mss in to two recensions namely A of the later origin & the B of the earlier origin, and mentions following findings⁷:

1. In A sets about 40 verses are omitted as mere interpolation at the end of the chapter 5th, while B sets give them ;
2. The 9th chapter in A sets is divided in to two chapters (IX & X) in B and thus the numbering differs thenceforth ;
3. The Chapters 14th & 15th in A dealing with prosody for the stage introduced later terminology of Pingala (as ra, ga, ta, bha, sa etc.), while the B sets merely equate the major of a line in short and long syllables of *laghu* and *guru* ;
4. The definitions in the 16th chapter are given in Upajati metres and in a certain order in A but they are given in Anuṣṭub metre and in a reverse order in the 17th chapter of the B sets ;
5. The subject matter of the 26th chapter in A is found in the 35th chapter in B sets ;
6. 36th chapter in B sets is divided in to two chapters 36 and 37 in A sets, or even as 38th in one of the copies of the A recension.

Here I am giving a comparative study of three different editions on the base of divisions of chapters, their names and the number of verses.

Gaekwad's Oriental Series, Baroda, Gaekward's Oriental Series, Baroda, (Vol-I, Second Edition, 1956), (Vol-II, First Edition, 1934), (Vol- III, Second Edition, 1954), (Vol- IV, Second Edition, 1964),		Reprint Edition of Kāvyamālā Series, Nirnaya Sagar Press, Bombay Edited by Pandit Kedarnath Published by Bharatiya Vidya Prakashan, Delhi-7.		Prof. M.M.Ghosh Edition, New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, India, First Edition-2006.		
Chapter #	Name of the Chapters	Number of Verses	Name of the Chapters	Number of Verses	Name of the Chapters	Number of Verses
I.	नाट्योत्पत्तिः	127	नाट्योत्पत्तिः	128	नाट्योत्पत्तिः	129
II.	मण्डपविधानः	105	मण्डपविधानं	111	मण्डपविधानं	104
III.	रङ्गदैवतपूजनं	102	रङ्गदैवतपूजाविधानं	102	रङ्गदैवतपूजाविधानं	101
IV.	ताण्डवलक्षणं	320	ताण्डवलक्षणं	326	ताण्डवलक्षणं	329
V.	पूर्वरङ्गविधानं	174+	पूर्वरङ्गविधानं	220	पूर्वरङ्गविधानं	218
		39				

5 अभिनवभारती, *Introductory Shloka No.26, ed. by Prof. Puspendra Kumar, New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi-11007, India. 2006*

6 *Ibid, Page no.6,*

7 M. Ramakrishna kavi, *preface, Nāṭyaśāstra, Vol -I, page 60, Gaekward's Oriental Series, Baroda, Second Edition, 1956.*

VI.	रसाध्यायः	83	रसाध्यायः	84	रसाध्यायः	83
VII.	भावव्यञ्जकः	121	भावव्यञ्जनः	130	भावव्यञ्जनः	125
VIII.	उत्तमाङ्गाभिनयः	177	उपाङ्गाभिनयः	174	अङ्गाभिनयः	173
IX.	अङ्गाभिनयः	283	अङ्गाभिनयः	267	उपाङ्गाभिनयः	323
X.	चारीविधानं	103	चारीविधानं	102	शारीराभिनयः	54
XI.	मण्डलकल्पनं	70	मण्डलकल्पनं	63	चारीविधानं	101
XII.	गतिप्रचारः	248	गतिप्रचारः	187	मण्डलविधानं	68
XIII.	कक्ष्याप्रवृत्तिधर्मीव्यञ्जकः	86	करयुक्तिधर्मीव्यञ्जकः	79	कक्ष्याविभागविधानं	228
XIV.	छन्दोविधानं	133	छन्दोविधानं	120	छन्दोविधानं	77
XV.	छन्दोविचितिः	227	छन्दोवृत्तविधिः	172	वृत्तलक्षणं	103
XVI.	काव्यलक्षणः	128+	अलङ्कारलक्षणं	124	लक्षणालङ्काराः	172
		41				
XVII.	काकुस्वरव्यञ्जनः	150	काकुस्वरविधानं	137	वाग्लक्षणानि	159
XVIII.	दशरूपनिरूपणं	126	दशरूपलक्षणं	198	भाषालक्षणं	61
XIX.	सन्धिभिरूपणं	154	सन्ध्यङ्गविकल्पः	133	काकुस्वरूपव्यञ्जकः	77
XX.	वृत्तिविकल्पनं	77	वृत्तिविकल्पः	66	दशरूपलक्षणं	150
XXI.	आहार्याभिनयः	227	आहार्याभिनयः	214	सन्ध्यङ्गविकल्पः	129
XXII.	सामान्याभिनयः	332	सामान्याभिनयः	321	वृत्तिविकल्पः	65
XXIII.	वैशिकः	80	वैशिकः	73	आहार्याभिनयः	223
XXIV.	स्त्रीपुंसोपचारः	89	सामान्याभिनयः	116	सामान्याभिनयः	328
XXV.	चित्राभिनयः	125	चित्राभिनयः	130	नाट्योपचारः	79
XXVI.	विकृतिविकल्पः	38	प्रकृतिविकल्पः	26	चित्राभिनयः	129
XXVII.	सिद्धिव्यञ्जकः	104	सिद्धिव्यञ्जकः	93	सिद्धिव्यञ्जकः	104
XXVIII.	जातिविकल्पनं	141	जातिलक्षणं	161	आतोद्यविधिः	151
XXIX.	ततातोद्यविधानं	119/147	आतोद्यजातिविधानः	125	ततातोद्यविधानं	156
XXX.	सुषिरातोद्यलक्षणं	12	सुषिरातोद्यविधानः	13	सुषिरातोद्यविधानं	13
XXXI.	तालाध्यायः	378	तालविधानः	334	तालव्यञ्जकः	502
XXXII.	ध्रुवाविधानः	437	ध्रुवाध्यायः	442	ध्रुवाविधानः	525
XXXIII.	गुणदोषविचारः	23	गुणाध्यायः	22	पुष्करवाद्यः	301
XXXIV.	पुष्करवाद्यः	304/246	पुष्करवाद्यः	259	प्रकृतिविचारः	99
XXXV.	भूमिविकल्पः	41	भूमिविकल्पः	39	भूमिविकल्पः	109
XXXVI.	नटशापः	50	नटशापः	45	नाट्यावतारः	83
XXXVII.	गुह्यतत्त्वकथनं	31	गुह्यविकल्पः	33		

The above comparison indicates that the editions of the Nāṭyaśāstra have many variants in the content and number of verses of the chapters, which is quite natural because the editions have been prepared on the base of different mss based on different recensions, scribed in

different periods and collected from various parts of India and abroad. Even these variations had been seen in many available recensions of Nāṭyaśāstra, during the period of Abhinavagupta as it is mentioned in The Abhinavabhāratī: तथा च मतान्तरेण भरतमुनिरेवान्यथाप्युद्देशलक्षणेन

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नामान्तरैरपि च व्यवहारं करोति; तत एव पुस्तकेषु भेदो दृश्यते तं च दर्शयिष्यामः।¹

The Number of chapters are 37 in *GOS* & *Kāvyaṃālā* where as 36 in *Chowkhamba* & Prof. M.M.Ghosh Edition, *New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, India*, first Edition-2006.

The critical examinations explore that the chapter 9th of *GOS* is split up in to two chapters 9th and 10th in *Chowkhamba* edition. The chapter 17th of *GOS* is again split up in to chapter 18th and 19th in *Chowkhamba* edition. The chapter 24th of *GOS* reads as the 34th in *Chowkhamba* edition. The chapter 26th of *GOS* reads along with the chapter 35th of *Chowkhamba* edition.

The Chapters 32nd and 33rd of *GOS* are combined in to a single chapter 32nd of *Chowkhamba* edition. This combination was acceptable to *Abhinavagupta* as he has discussed the reasons there of, i.e.

“ननु गान्धर्वमुखेन भागवद्भानमिह लक्षयितुमारब्धम्। गान्धर्वस्यैव च स्वरविधिरध्यायत्रयेण (अ. 28,29,30) दर्शितः। तालविधिरध्यायेन (अ. 32) च। तत्रैव पदविधिरपि दर्शितः”²

In the chapter 28th the definitions of *jātis* are given in both prose and verse in almost all the recensions. *Abhinavagupta* has followed the prose version of *jātis*. *Ramakrishna Kavi* put the definitions in verse in parenthesis and has not assigned serial numbers considering those to be interpolated³.

Ramakrishna Kavi has mentioned two different readings of each of chapter 29th and 34th. These readings could have been collated with the text considered to be primary and the variants could have been given in foot notes.

While deciding the primary text of *Nāṭyaśāstra*

we should investigate whether the number of *rasas* according to *Bharata* was eight or nine! All the major editions the *GOS*, *Kāvyaṃālā* read that :

शुङ्गारहास्यकरुणा रौद्रवीरभयानकाः।
बीभत्साद्भुतसंज्ञौ चेत्यष्टौ नाट्ये रसाः स्मृताः॥⁵

But *Abhinavagupta* agrees to take nine *rasas* including *śānta* as a *rasa* as he affirms that : “तस्मादस्ति शान्तो रसः। तथा च चिरन्तनपुस्तकेषु ‘स्थायिभावान् रसत्वमुपनेष्यामः’ इत्यनन्तर ‘शान्तो नाम शमस्थायिभावात्मकः’ इत्यादिशान्तलक्षणं पठ्यते”⁶ This statement of *Abhinavagupta* is based on a different recension of *Nāṭyaśāstra* that reads as: “अथ शान्तो नाम शमस्थायिभावात्मको मोक्षप्रवर्तकः। स तु तत्त्वज्ञानवैराग्याशयशुद्ध्यादिभिर्विभावैः समुत्पद्यते। तस्य यमनियमाध्यात्मध्यानधारणोपासनसर्वभूतदयालिङ्ग-ग्रहणादिभिरनुभावैरभिनयः प्रयोक्तव्यः। व्यभिचारिणश्चास्य निर्वदस्मृतिधृतिसर्वाश्रम-शौचस्तम्भरोमाञ्चादयः। अत्रार्याः श्लोकाश्च भवन्ति – मोक्षाध्यात्मसमुत्थस्तत्त्वज्ञानार्थहेतुसंयुक्तः। निःश्रेयसोपदिष्टः शान्तरसो नाम सम्भवति॥”⁷ But the controversy lies as it is when we find *Kālidāsa* mentioning in his *Vikramorvaśīya* that : मुनिना भरतेन यः प्रयोगो भवतीष्वष्टरसाश्रयः प्रयुक्तः। ललिताभिनयं तमद्य भर्ता मरुतां द्रष्टुमनाः सलोकपालः॥⁸

This statement of *Kālidāsa* recognizing eight *rasas* that was acceptable to *Bharata* helps us to reach in to conclusion that the number of *rasas* acceptable to *Bharata* was eight only. The text favoring nine *rasas* may be an interpolation in the later recensions.

As there are about 40 verses starting from पुनश्चित्रे तथा मिश्रे are omitted at the end of chapter V in some mss, and Mr. M. *Ramakrishna kavi* states those to be interpolated and the commentary to that part was written by *Kohala*.⁹ But it is clear

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1 *Abhinavagupta, Abhinavabhāratī, Page 545, Chapter – XVII, Vol. II, Nāṭyaśāstra, Prof. M.M. Ghosh Edition, New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, India, 2006.*

2 P. 301 of अभिनवभारती, Gaekward's Oriental Series, Baroda, Vol-IV, Second Edition, 1964.

3 See Chapter 32nd of Nāṭyaśāstra of Gaekward's Oriental Series, Baroda, Vol-IV, Second Edition, 1964.

4 Ibid.

5 15/6, Gaekward's Oriental Series, Baroda, Vol-I, Second Edition, 1956 & Reprint Edition of Kavyamala Series, Nirnaya Sagar Press, Bombay, edited by, Pandit Kedarnath, Published by Bharatiya Vidya Prakashan, Delhi-7.

6 Page – 339, Gaekward's Oriental Series, Baroda, Vol-I, Second Edition, 1956.

7 Ibid, page – 333-334. & page – 103-104, Reprint Edition of Kavyamala Series, Nirnaya Sagar Press, Bombay, edited by, Pandit Kedarnath, Published by Bharatiya Vidya Prakashan, Delhi-7.

8 II.18, Vikramorvaśīya.

9 Page – 251, Gaekward's Oriental Series, Baroda, Vol-I, Second Edition, 1956.

that the content of those 40 verses are the part of *pūrvaranga* that is described in the chapter V and hence do not appear to be an interpolation what Mr. Kavi has mentioned.

At the beginning of the 16th Chapter in GOS the lakṣaṇas are described in Upajāti metre ; i.e.

विभूषणं चाक्षरसंहतिश्च शोभाभिमानौ गुणकीर्तनं च।
प्रोत्साहनोदाहरणे निरुक्तं गुणानुवादोऽतिशयः सहेतुः॥
सारूप्यमित्याध्यवसायसिद्धिपदोच्चयाक्रन्दमनोरथाश्च।
आख्यानयाच्या प्रतिषेधपृच्छा दृष्टान्तनिर्भासनसंशयाश्च॥
आशीः प्रियोक्तिः कपटः क्षमा च प्राप्तिश्च पश्चात्तपनं तथैव।
अर्थानुवृत्तीर्ह्युपपत्तियुक्ती कार्योनुनीतिः परिदेवनं च॥
षट्त्रिंशदेतानि तु लक्षणानि प्रोक्तानि वै भूषणसंज्ञितानि।
काव्येषु भावार्थगतानि तज्ज्ञैः सम्यक्प्रयोज्यानि यथारसं तु॥¹⁰

Whereas those are described in *anuṣṭup* meter in the (17th chapter) in *Chowkhamba & Prof. M.M.Ghosh Edition* as follow:

भूषणाक्षरसंघातौ शोभोदाहरणे तथा।
हेतुसंशयदृष्टान्ताः प्राप्त्यभिप्राय एव च॥
निदर्शनं निरुक्तं च सिद्धिश्चाथ विशेषणम्।
गुणातिपातातिशयौ तुल्यतर्कः पदोच्चयः॥
दिष्टं चैवोपदिष्टं च विचारस्तद्विपर्ययः।
भ्रंशश्चानुनयो माला दाक्षिण्यं गर्हणं तथा॥
अर्थापत्तिः प्रसिद्धिश्च पृच्छा सारूप्यमेव च।
मनोरथश्च लेशश्च संक्षोभो गुणकीर्तनम्॥
ज्ञेया ह्यनुक्तसिद्धिश्च प्रियं वचनमेव च।
षट्त्रिंशल्लक्षणान्येवंकाव्यबन्धेषुनिर्दिशेत्॥¹¹

The readings in *anuṣṭup* meter appear to be the primary, as the following verses of the same chapter are in *anuṣṭup* only.

Therefore, the variants available in the text of *Nāṭyaśāstra* in different recensions are due to the base mss collected from different parts of India and abroad, scribed in different periods. There is not even a single edition of *Nāṭyaśāstra*, that can claim to be the primary one. So a critical and thorough observation with a comparative study can make it possible to reach the primary text of *Nāṭyaśāstra*. Following points should be adhered to find out the an authentic text, as such ;

1. The available mss and their chronological history and geographical origin.
2. Comparison of the text with the commentaries of Abhinavagupta.
3. The Content and order of the text.
4. The language and style of the text.
5. The reference and citations of *Nāṭyaśāstra* in other texts of dramaturgy and treatises of poetries and dramas.
6. The reference and citations of other texts of dramaturgy and allied treatises in *Nāṭyaśāstra*.

The *sāradā* mss is yet to be traced out. Therefore, Finally, from the above study it could be summed up that the reconstruction of the text of the *Nāṭyaśāstra* of Bharata is inevitable to get an authentic and primary version.

Bibliography

1. History of Sanskrit Poetics by P.V.Kane, *Motilal Banarasi Dass*, Delhi, India, Reprint of the fourth edition, 1987.
2. *Nāṭyaśāstra* ed. by Prof. Puspendra Kumar, introduction page – XIX, translated in to English by M.M.Ghosh, New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, India, 2006.
3. *Nāṭyaśāstra* ed. by M. Ramakrishna Kavi, Preface, Vol –I, page 60, Gaekwad's Oriental Series, Baroda, Second Edition, 1956.
4. *Nāṭyaśāstra* ed. by Reprint Edition of Kavyamala Series, Nirnaya Sagar Press, Bombay, edited by, Pandit Kedarnath, Published by Bharatiya Vidya Prakashan, Delhi-7
5. *Nāṭyaśāstra* ed. by Pandit Batukanath Sharma and Pandit Baladeva Upadhyaya published a complete edition with 36 chapters based on two different manuscripts of *Nāṭyaśāstra* in the *Kāśī Sanskrit series* mostly quoted as *Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series* in 1929.

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10 16.1-5 Gaekwad's Oriental Series, Baroda, Gaekwad's Oriental Series, Baroda, (Vol-II, First Edition, 1934),

11 17.1-5, Prof. M.M. Ghosh Edition, New Bharatiya cor New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, India, 2006.